

Advanced Deep Learning Models in Earth Observation for Urban Applications: Bologna and Turin Case Studies

Navid Tavakoli Shalmani

DICAM, Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna

Corresponding author: navid.tavakoli@studio.unibo.it

Version: v1.0

Date: 20 November 2024

Abstract

This study investigates the application of deep learning models for building segmentation and footprint extraction using pansharpened satellite imagery, with the aim of supporting or optimizing urban data management and enhancing environmental resource management. Building footprint extraction is critical for identifying the exact spatial extent of structures, which can be used to inform various urban planning and resource management efforts. The study utilized panchromatic and multispectral satellite images from the WorldView-2 platform to assess multiple deep learning architectures, including UNet with attention mechanisms, DHAUNet with hybrid and multi-head attention configurations, and several iterations of DEEPLabV3 with ResNet backbones. Among these, DEEPLabV3 with ResNet-50, tested across different tile sizes (1024, 512, and 256), demonstrated the highest accuracy in extracting building footprints, with optimal results achieved using a 256×256 tile size. The refined model was applied to datasets from two cities - Turin and Bologna - representing distinct urban roof architectures. Additionally, a combined dataset facilitated comparative analysis of segmentation performance across varying urban environments. The results emphasize the model's adaptability and precision in extracting building footprints, demonstrating its robustness across diverse architectural contexts. This research contributes to the advancement of deep learning integration with satellite remote sensing, providing valuable insights for future applications in sustainable urban development. Furthermore, the findings underscore the potential for leveraging accurate building footprint data to support renewable energy initiatives, disaster risk management, and improved urban planning practices globally.

Keywords: building segmentation; pansharpening; WorldView-2; DeepLabV3; urban analytics; remote sensing, computer vision, Deep learning

1. Introduction

The rapid growth of urban areas has highlighted the need for innovative tools to support urban planning and environmental management. Satellite imaging, particularly pansharpened imagery that combines panchromatic and multispectral data, has emerged as a valuable resource for mapping urban structures. Recent advances in deep learning have further enhanced the potential of satellite data, enabling accurate segmentation of complex urban environments (Pohl and Genderen, 1998; Zhu et al., 2017).

Building segmentation involves delineating structures at a pixel level, which is crucial for applications such as solar panel placement, rainwater harvesting, and urban zoning (Singh and Reddy, 2014). However, traditional methods often fall short in handling the diversity of urban layouts. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have proven effective in automating segmentation tasks, particularly in cities with varied architectural features (Hoeser et al., 2020). This research evaluates the adaptability of deep learning models in building segmentation, using Bologna and Turin as case studies to test performance in dense and structured urban environments, respectively.

2. Methodology

2.1. Data Collection and Preparation

The study utilized high-resolution WorldView-2 satellite imagery, renowned for its panchromatic (0.46 m) and multispectral (1.85 m) bands, which are critical for detailed urban mapping (Navalgund, 2017). Pansharpening was performed using GDAL tools within QGIS to enhance the spatial resolution of multispectral images while preserving spectral integrity (Vivone, 2019). Figure 1 illustrates a pansharpened image of Bologna.

Figure 1 Pansharpened Satellite Image of Bologna.

Ground truth masks, obtained from the Geoportale of Comune di Torino and the Open Data portal of Comune di Bologna, were converted into binary black-and-white segmentation maps. This preprocessing ensured clarity and uniformity for training the models (municipality of Turin, 2024; municipality of Bologna, 2024).

2.2. Deep Learning Architectures

This section presents three advanced deep learning architectures used in the study, each tailored for building segmentation tasks in urban environments. These models, UNet with attention mechanisms, DHAUNet variants, and DEEPLabV3 with ResNet backbones, employ innovative strategies to enhance feature extraction and segmentation accuracy.

2.2.1. UNet with Attention Mechanisms

UNet features a symmetric encoder-decoder structure with skip connections, which retain spatial information essential for precise segmentation. The model has been enhanced with attention mechanisms to adaptively focus on critical regions in the input imagery, suppressing irrelevant details like vegetation or roads, making it particularly effective in dense urban areas (Serag et al., 2019).

Encoder (Downsampling Path): The encoder captures the context of the input image through a series of convolutional and pooling layers. Each layer extracts features at different scales, increasing the field of view and enabling the model to understand broader spatial contexts.

Decoder (Upsampling Path): The decoder reconstructs the segmentation map by progressively increasing the resolution of feature maps using transposed convolutions (deconvolutions). Skip connections integrate spatial details lost during downsampling, enhancing precision.

Skip Connections: These connections link encoder and decoder layers directly, ensuring that fine-grained spatial features are preserved in the output segmentation map.

Attention UNet: This variant incorporates attention mechanisms into the skip connections. These modules weigh features passed from the encoder to the decoder, prioritizing relevant data and filtering out noise. This functionality is crucial for distinguishing between closely packed or visually similar structures like buildings and roads in urban environments (Zhu et al., 2017).

Figure 2 UNet architecture. Serag et al., 2019.

2.2.2. DHAUNet Variants

DHAUNet extends UNet by introducing Dual Hybrid Attention mechanisms that integrate spatial and channel-wise attention, enhancing the network's ability to identify intricate relationships across urban landscapes.

Spatial Attention: Highlights important spatial regions, such as building footprints, while downplaying less relevant areas.

Channel-Wise Attention: Emphasizes significant spectral features, aiding in distinguishing structures with similar spatial patterns but different materials.

Multi-Head Attention: Inspired by transformers, this mechanism allows the model to focus on multiple feature subspaces simultaneously. Such versatility improves segmentation performance in complex scenarios, such as overlapping or irregularly shaped buildings commonly found in urban areas like Bologna and Turin (Sun et al., 2022).

Figure 3 Dual Hybrid Attention, Sun et al., 2022.

2.2.3. DEEPLabV3 with Resnet Backbones

DEEPLabV3 represents a state-of-the-art model for semantic segmentation, designed to capture multi-scale features efficiently. The architecture integrates **atrous convolution** and **Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling (ASPP)** to address variations in object scale and complexity, making it particularly suited for urban environments (Chen et al., 2017).

- **Atrous Convolution (Dilated Convolution):** Expands the field of view of convolutional filters, enabling the model to incorporate larger spatial contexts without increasing computational cost. This is especially beneficial for detecting objects of varying scales, such as rooftops and large building complexes.
- **ResNet Backbones (ResNet-50 and ResNet-101):** DEEPLabV3 employs ResNet backbones for efficient feature extraction. The residual connections in ResNet address the vanishing gradient problem, facilitating deeper network training. While ResNet-50 offers a balance between computational efficiency and accuracy, ResNet-101 provides greater depth for more detailed feature representation (He et al., 2016).

- **ASPP (Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling):** ASPP captures contextual information at multiple scales by applying filters with varying dilation rates. This enables the model to handle both fine details and broader spatial patterns critical for urban segmentation tasks (Chen et al., 2017).

Figure 4 DEEPLabV3 architecture(Chen et al., 2017).

2.3. Model Training and Evaluation

The training and evaluation of the models were conducted with a rigorous framework to ensure optimal performance and reliable results. This process involved dataset preparation, data augmentation, model training, and performance evaluation using comprehensive metrics. (Karimi and Sultana, 2024).

2.3.1. Data Preparation

The WorldView-2 satellite imagery was preprocessed into tiles of sizes 256×256 , 512×512 , and 1024×1024 pixels to facilitate training. The smaller tile size (256×256) allowed for better handling of complex urban features, while larger tiles provided broader contextual information. The dataset was divided into three subsets:

- **Training Set (70%):** Used for optimizing model parameters.
- **Validation Set (15%):** Monitored the model's performance during training to prevent overfitting.
- **Test Set (15%):** Used exclusively for evaluating the final trained model.

Figure 5 Steps in Deep Learning Model Development for Image Segmentation.

Ground truth masks were binarized into black (background) and white (buildings) to match the segmentation task's requirements.

2.3.2. Data Augmentation

To increase variability and robustness, data augmentation techniques such as rotation, flipping, scaling, and random cropping were applied. This step ensured that the models could generalize across diverse urban scenarios, reducing the risk of overfitting.

The augmentation process can be mathematically expressed as transformations applied to an input image X :

$$X' = T(X)$$

where T represents a series of transformations such as rotation (R), flipping (F), and scaling (S):

$$T(X) = S(F(R(X)))$$

2.3.3. Model Training Pipeline

The models were implemented using PyTorch and trained on Google Colab, leveraging NVIDIA A100 GPUs for accelerated computations. Training parameters were carefully optimized as follows:

- **Batch Size:** Set to 8, balancing memory usage and gradient stability.
- **Optimizer:** Adam optimizer was employed due to its effectiveness in handling sparse gradients and noisy data. Its parameter update rule is given by:

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \frac{\eta}{\sqrt{v_t} + \epsilon} m_t$$

where:

θ_t : Model parameters at step t

η : Learning rate

m_t : Exponentially weighted moving average of gradients (momentum term)

v_t : Exponentially weighted moving average of squared gradients (RMSProp term)

ϵ : Smoothing term to avoid division by zero.

- **Learning Rate:** Initialized at 0.0001 and adjusted using the ReduceLROnPlateau scheduler, which reduces the learning rate if the validation loss plateaued.
- **Loss Function:** Binary Cross-Entropy Loss was used to train the models, defined as:

$$L = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - \hat{y}_i)]$$

where y_i is the true label, \hat{y}_i is the predicted probability, and N is the number of pixels.

2.3.4. Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate the models, several metrics were employed to capture different aspects of performance:

Accuracy

Accuracy is a basic metric that measures the proportion of correctly classified pixels in the image.

It is calculated as:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}}$$

F1 Score

It is the weighted average of Precision and Recall. Therefore, this score takes both false positives and false negatives into account. It is especially useful when the class distribution is uneven.

$$\text{F1 Score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

Precision

It is the ratio of correctly predicted positive results to the total number of predicted positive results. It is a measure of the accuracy of the positive predictions.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Where:

TP is the number of true positives.

FP is the number of false positives. (**False Positive:** The model incorrectly thinks the positive class is present when it's not.)

Recall (Sensitivity)

It is the ratio of correctly predicted positive instances to the total number of actual positive instances in the dataset. It shows how many of the actual positives were correctly identified by the model as positive (True Positive).

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

Where:

FN is the number of false negatives. (**False Negative:** The model incorrectly thinks the positive class is absent when it is actually present.)

Figure 6 Explanation of TP, FP, and FN.

Dice Coefficient

Figure 7 Explanation of Dice Coefficient, and Intersection over Union (IoU).

The Dice coefficient is a measure of overlap more than a conventional accuracy. It is very similar to the F1 score.

$$Dice = \frac{2 \times |A \cap B|}{|A| + |B|}$$

Where:

A and B are the predicted and true masks, respectively.

$|A \cap B|$ represents the common elements between A and B (the intersection).

$|A|$ and $|B|$ are the sums of all elements in each set.

The script calculates the Dice coefficient as follows:

Intersection over Union (IoU)

IoU, also known as the Jaccard Index, is a statistic used to gauge the similarity and diversity of sample sets.

$$IoU = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}$$

Where:

$|A \cup B|$ is the union of the predicted set A and the truth set B .

Mean Squared Error (MSE)

MSE measures the average of the squares of the errors that is, the average squared difference between the estimated values and the actual value.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \bar{Y}_i)^2$$

Where:

Y_i is the true value and \bar{Y}_i is the predicted value.

2.3.5. Evaluation Process

During the evaluation phase, the trained models were applied to the test dataset. Predictions were compared against ground truth masks using the above metrics. The outputs were thresholded (e.g., at 0.5) to produce binary segmentation maps. Metrics were averaged across the dataset to ensure robust performance assessment

3. Results

This chapter presents the results of the segmentation experiments, detailing the performance of all tested models in 3.1 and focusing on the best-performing model in 3.2.

3.1. Comparative Results of All Models

The performance of three deep learning architectures—UNet with attention mechanisms, DHAUNet variants, and DEEPLabV3 with ResNet-50 backbones—was evaluated using datasets from Bologna and Turin. Table 1 summarizes the evaluation metrics, including accuracy, Dice coefficient, Intersection over Union (IoU), precision, recall, and mean squared error (MSE).

Table 1 Models evaluation results.

ID	Model Name	Accuracy	Dice	IoU	MSE	Precision	Recall	F1
1	UNet with Attention Mechanism	0.9159	0.8367	0.7966	0.0474	0.8179	0.8055	0.8023
2	DHAUNet+UNet	0.9163	0.8415	0.8012	0.0462	0.8303	0.7943	0.8022
3	DHAUNet Multihead	0.9140	0.8403	0.7986	0.0482	0.8047	0.8189	0.8019
4	First Model 512×512 Turin	0.9114	0.8200	0.7522	0.0641	0.8269	0.8202	0.8213
5	First Model 512×512 Bologna	0.9020	0.8036	0.7320	0.0707	0.8554	0.7877	0.8162
6	First Model 512×512 Turin & Bologna	0.9104	0.8178	0.7481	0.0674	0.8421	0.8252	0.8318
7	Second Model 512×512 Turin	0.8321	0.7582	0.6580	0.0794	0.8090	0.7663	0.7853
8	Second Model 512×512 Bologna	0.8360	0.7636	0.6654	0.0762	0.8271	0.7602	0.7907
9	Second Model 512×512 Turin & Bologna	0.8383	0.7654	0.6686	0.0754	0.8180	0.7775	0.7957
10	First Model 256×256 Turin	0.9303	0.8256	0.7711	0.0521	0.8602	0.8329	0.8450
11	First Model 256×256 Bologna	0.9275	0.8283	0.7662	0.0541	0.8707	0.8178	0.8406
12	First Model 256×256 Turin & Bologna	0.9273	0.8182	0.7613	0.0535	0.8657	0.8047	0.8322
13	Second Model 256×256 Turin	0.9327	0.8341	0.7818	0.0519	0.8660	0.8389	0.8504
14	Second Model 256×256 Bologna	0.9353	0.8491	0.7920	0.0516	0.8611	0.8502	0.8532
15	Second Model 256×256 Turin & Bologna	0.9327	0.8340	0.7808	0.0524	0.8591	0.8406	0.8477

From Table 1, it is evident that DEEPLabV3 with ResNet-50 outperformed the other models across all metrics. Its ability to adapt to architectural complexities and achieve higher segmentation accuracy makes it the best-performing model.

3.2. Performance Analysis of DEEPLabV3 with ResNet-50

DEEPLabV3 with ResNet-50, the top-performing model, achieved the highest scores in accuracy, Dice coefficient, and IoU across both Bologna and Turin datasets. This section provides a detailed analysis of its results and visual segmentation outputs.

Quantitative Results

Table 2 highlights the detailed performance metrics of DEEPLabV3 with ResNet-50 on the Bologna, Turin, and combined datasets.

Table 2 Detailed Metrics of DEEPLabV3 with ResNet-50 (256×256 Tiles)

Dataset	Accuracy	Dice Coefficient	IoU	Precision	Recall	MSE
Bologna	93.53%	84.91%	79.20%	86.11%	83.45%	5.16%
Turin	93.27%	83.41%	78.18%	86.60%	82.70%	5.19%
Combined	93.27%	83.40%	78.08%	85.91%	82.91%	5.24%

The high Dice coefficient and IoU values reflect the model’s capability to segment building footprints accurately, even in complex urban scenarios like Bologna's dense historical center and Turin's structured grid layout.

Visual Results

Figures 1, 2 and 3 present the visual segmentation outputs for Bologna, Turin, and combined datasets respectively. These maps illustrate the accuracy of building footprint delineation and the potential for practical urban planning applications.

Table 3 Results of Bologna Dataset.

Test image	Ground truth mask	First model prediction	Second model prediction

Table 4 Results of Turin Dataset

Test image	Ground truth mask	First model prediction	Second model prediction

Table 5 Results of Dataset.

Test image	Ground truth mask	First model prediction	Second model prediction

Qualitative Insights

The model's performance underscores its adaptability to varying architectural complexities:

- **Bologna Dataset:** Despite challenges posed by dense and irregular building layouts, DEEPLabV3 successfully segmented rooftops with minimal errors.
- **Turin Dataset:** The structured urban layout of Turin allowed for higher segmentation precision, with clear delineation between buildings and non-building areas.

These results validate the model's robustness and scalability for diverse urban environments.

4. Discussion

This chapter discusses the key findings from the deep learning models applied to satellite imagery of Turin and Bologna. Instead of reanalyzing the technical details of segmentation accuracy and metrics, the emphasis will be on the practical implications of these results for urban planning, including applications like solar panel installation in Turin and potential rainwater harvesting in Bologna. A comparative analysis between the two cities is also included, highlighting unique architectural influences and identifying opportunities for further research.

4.1. Model Performance and Insights

The results affirm the superiority of DEEPLabV3 with ResNet-50 in segmenting urban structures from pansharpened satellite imagery. The model's use of Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling (ASPP) enhances its ability to capture multi-scale features, making it highly effective for both large and small urban structures.

Bologna's dense and irregular urban landscape posed challenges that were effectively addressed by DEEPLabV3's contextual feature extraction capabilities. Turin's more structured urban layout allowed for precise segmentation with minimal errors, further demonstrating the model's adaptability.

4.2. Applications:

The segmentation outputs provide valuable insights for sustainable urban planning:

Renewable Energy Planning: The segmented building data identifies rooftops suitable for solar panel installations, optimizing energy generation potential in urban areas.

Water Resource Management: Building segmentation informs the design of rainwater harvesting systems, addressing challenges like urban flooding and water scarcity.

5. Conclusion

This study confirms the efficacy of advanced deep learning models for urban building segmentation using pansharpened satellite imagery. DEEPLabV3 with ResNet-50 consistently demonstrated superior performance, achieving high accuracy and adaptability across diverse urban settings. The model's ability to handle varying architectural complexities positions it as a valuable tool for sustainable urban development.

5.1 Contributions

The findings contribute to the growing integration of remote sensing and deep learning in urban planning by:

Improving the precision of building segmentation for renewable energy and water management projects.

Providing scalable methods for analyzing diverse urban environments, aligning with global sustainability goals.

5.2 Limitations and Future Work

While DEEPLabV3 with ResNet-50 showed excellent results, its computational requirements remain a challenge. Future research could focus on optimizing model architectures for real-time applications and extending the methodology to additional cities with varying architectural features. Integrating these models with IoT and dynamic urban monitoring systems could further enhance their utility for smart city initiatives.

This work underscores the potential of deep learning and remote sensing integration to support global sustainability efforts and drive innovation in urban planning.

Bibliography

- Adegun, Adekanmi Adeyinka, Jean Vincent Fonou-Dombeu, Serestina Viriri, e John Odindi. 2024. “Ontology-Based Deep Learning Model for Object Detection and Image Classification in Smart City Concepts”. *Smart Cities* 7 (4): 2182–2207. <https://doi.org/10.3390/smartcities7040086>.
- Asokan, Anju, J Anitha, Monica Ciobanu, Andrei Gabor, Antoanela Naaji, e D Jude Hemanth. 2020. “Image Processing Techniques for Analysis of Satellite Images for Historical Maps Classification—An Overview”. *Applied Sciences* 10 (12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10124207>.
- Chen, Liang-Chieh, George Papandreou, Florian Schroff, e Hartwig Adam. 2017. “Rethinking Atrous Convolution for Semantic Image Segmentation”. *CoRR* abs/1706.05587. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1706.05587>.
- Comune di Bologna. 2024. “Open Data - Bologna Dataset”. Geoportale Comune di Bologna. 2024. https://opendata.comune.bologna.it/explore/dataset/rifiter_edif_pl/export/?refine.tipologia=Edificio+generico&basemap=85181b&location=20,44.5143,11.34613.
- Comune di Torino. 2024. “Geoportale Comune di Torino”. Geoportale Comune di Torino. 2024. <http://geoportale.comune.torino.it/web/cartografia/cartografia-scarico>.
- El-Agamy, Rasha F, Hanaa A Sayed, Arwa M AL Akhatatneh, Mansourah Aljohani, e Mostafa Elhosseini. 2024. “Comprehensive analysis of digital twins in smart cities: a 4200-paper bibliometric study”. *Artificial Intelligence Review* 57 (6): 154. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10462-024-10781-8>.
- European Space Agency (ESA). 2023. “WorldView-2 Satellite ”. ESA Earth Online. 2023. <https://earth.esa.int/eogateway/missions/worldview-2>.
- GeoSage. 2023. “HighView Image Fusion and Pan-Sharpening Software”. GeoSage Website. 7 de janeiro de 2023. <https://www.geosage.com/highview/imagefusion.html>.
- Hoeser, Thorsten, Felix Bachofer, e Claudia Kuenzer. 2020. “Object Detection and Image Segmentation with Deep Learning on Earth Observation Data: A Review—Part II: Applications”. *Remote Sensing* 12 (18). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12183053>.
- Independent Group of Scientists appointed by the Secretary-General. 2023. “Global Sustainable Development Report 2023: Times of crisis, times of change: Science for accelerating transformations to sustainable development”. New York. <https://sdgs.un.org/gsdrr/gsdrr2023>.
- Jiang, Jieli, Xiangming Hong, Yingnan Zhao, Xiaonglong Xu, e Yan Cui. 2023. “SDAUNet: A simple dual attention mechanism UNet for mixed noise removal”. *IET Image Processing* 17 (13): 3884–96. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1049/ipr2.12905>.
- Karimi, Firoozeh, e Selima Sultana. 2024. “Urban Expansion Prediction and Land Use/Land Cover Change Modeling for Sustainable Urban Development”. *Sustainability* 16 (6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16062285>.
- Kaur, Gurpreet, Kamaljit Singh Saini, Dilbag Singh, e Manjit Kaur. 2021. “A Comprehensive Study on Computational Pansharpening Techniques for Remote Sensing Images”. *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering* 28 (7): 4961–78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11831-021-09565-y>.

- Khan, Dawood, Abdur Raziq, Hsu-Wen Vincent Young, Tariq Sardar, e Yuei-An Liou. 2022. "Identifying Potential Sites for Rainwater Harvesting Structures in Ghazi Tehsil, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, Using Geospatial Approach". *Remote Sensing* 14 (19). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14195008>.
- Khryashev Vladimir, e Ivanovsky Leonid. 2019. "Urban areas analysis using satellite image segmentation and deep neural network". *E3S Web Conf.* 135:1064. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/201913501064>.
- Kim, Danu, Jeongkyung Won, Eunji Lee, Kyung Ryul Park, Jihee Kim, Sangyoon Park, Hyunjoo Yang, e Meeyoung Cha. 2022. "Disaster assessment using computer vision and satellite imagery: Applications in detecting water-related building damages". *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.969758>.
- Li, Xiaomeng, Hao Chen, Xiaojuan Qi, Qi Dou, Chi-Wing Fu, e Pheng-Ann Heng. 2018. "H-DenseUNet: Hybrid Densely Connected UNet for Liver and Tumor Segmentation From CT Volumes". *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 37 (12): 2663–74. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2018.2845918>.
- Masi, Giuseppe, Davide Cozzolino, Luisa Verdoliva, e Giuseppe Scarpa. 2016. "Pansharpening by Convolutional Neural Networks". *Remote Sensing* 8 (7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs8070594>.
- Md Jelas, Imran, Mohd Asyraf Zulkifley, Mardina Abdullah, e Martin Spraggon. 2024. "Deforestation detection using deep learning-based semantic segmentation techniques: a systematic review". *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change* 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2024.1300060>.
- Navalgund, Ranganath, e M B Rajani. 2017. "The Science behind Archaeological Signatures from Space". *Current science* 113 (setembro):1859–72. <https://doi.org/10.18520/cs/v113/i10/1859-1872>.
- Nijhawan Rahul and Jindal, Radhika and Sharma Himanshu and Raman Balasubramanian and Das Josodhir. 2020. "A Deep Learning Framework Approach for Urban Area Classification Using Remote Sensing Data". Em *Proceedings of 3rd International Conference on Computer Vision and Image Processing*, editado por Masaki and Khanna Pritee and Kumar Sanjeev Chaudhuri Bidyut B. and Nakagawa, 449–56. Singapore: Springer Singapore.
- Panuju, Dyah R, David J Paull, e Amy L Griffin. 2020. "Change Detection Techniques Based on Multispectral Images for Investigating Land Cover Dynamics". *Remote Sensing* 12 (11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12111781>.
- Petrosino, Francesco. 2021. "Assessment of Rooftop Solar Photovoltaic potential through Spatial Analysis and Implementation of Machine Techniques". *Electronic, POLITECNICO DI TORINO*. <http://webthesis.biblio.polito.it/id/eprint/23207>.
- Pohl, C, e J L Van Genderen. 1998. "Review article Multisensor image fusion in remote sensing: Concepts, methods and applications". *International Journal of Remote Sensing* 19 (5): 823–54. <https://doi.org/10.1080/014311698215748>.
- Pradhan, Raseswari, e Jayaprakash Sahoo. 2019. "Smart Rainwater Management: New Technologies and Innovation". Em *Smart Urban Development*, editado por Vito Bobek. Rijeka: IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.86336>.
- Qi, Y, G Bitelli, E Mandanici, e F Trevisiol. 2023. "APPLICATION OF DEEP LEARNING CROP CLASSIFICATION MODEL BASED ON MULTISPECTRAL AND SAR SATELLITE IMAGERY". *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences XLVIII-1/W2-2023:1515–21*. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLVIII-1-W2-2023-1515-2023>.

- Radzali, N A W M, H Z M Shafri, M Norman, e S Saufi. 2018. "ROOFING ASSESSMENT FOR ROOFTOP RAINWATER HARVESTING ADOPTION USING REMOTE SENSING AND GIS APPROACH". *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences XLII-4/W9*:129–32. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-4-W9-129-2018>.
- Rainwater Management Solutions. 2024. "Rainwater Management Solutions". Rainwater Management Solutions. 2024. <https://rainwatermanagement.com/blogs/news/rainwater-harvesting>.
- Ronneberger Olaf and Fischer, Philipp and Brox Thomas. 2015. "U-Net: Convolutional Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation". Em *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention – MICCAI 2015*, editado por Joachim and Wells William M. and Frangi Alejandro F Navab Nassir and Hornegger, 234–41. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- S., Sreelakshmi, Vinod Chandra S. S., e E Shaji. 2022. "Landslide identification using machine learning techniques: Review, motivation, and future prospects". *Earth Science Informatics* 15 (4): 2063–90. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12145-022-00889-2>.
- Serag, Ahmed, Adrian Ion-Margineanu, Hammad Qureshi, Ryan McMillan, Marie-Judith Saint Martin, Jim Diamond, Paul O'Reilly, e Peter Hamilton. 2019. "Translational AI and Deep Learning in Diagnostic Pathology". *Frontiers in Medicine* 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2019.00185>.
- Singh, Dilpreet, e Chandan K Reddy. 2014. "A survey on platforms for big data analytics". *Journal of Big Data* 2 (1): 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40537-014-0008-6>.
- Sojka Sarah and Younos, Tamim and Crawford David. 2016. "Modern Urban Rainwater Harvesting Systems: Design, Case Studies, and Impacts". Em *Sustainable Water Management in Urban Environments*, editado por Tammy E Younos Tamim and Parece, 209–34. Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-29337-0_7.
- Solcast. 2024. "Solar Irradiance Data ". Solcast Website. 2024. <https://toolkit.solcast.com.au/>.
- Stewart, Adam J, Caleb Robinson, Isaac A Corley, Anthony Ortiz, Juan M Lavista Ferres, e Arindam Banerjee. 2021. "TorchGeo: deep learning with geospatial data". *CoRR* abs/2111.08872. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2111.08872>.
- Sun, Yu, Fukun Bi, Yangte Gao, Liang Chen, e Suting Feng. 2022. "A Multi-Attention UNet for Semantic Segmentation in Remote Sensing Images". *Symmetry* 14 (5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym14050906>.
- Taubenböck, H., & Dech, S. 2010. "Remote Sensing and Urban Planning: A Common Future." Sensors and Systems Website. 2010. <https://sensorsandsystems.com/remote-sensing-and-urban-planning-a-common-future/>.
- Tian, Yuxuan, Mengshan Duan, Xiangfen Cui, Qun Zhao, Senlin Tian, Yichao Lin, e Weicen Wang. 2023. "Advancing application of satellite remote sensing technologies for linking atmospheric and built environment to health". *Frontiers in Public Health* 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2023.1270033>.
- Trevisiol, Francesca, Alessandro Lambertini, Francesca Franci, e Emanuele Mandanici. 2022. "An Object-Oriented Approach to the Classification of Roofing Materials Using Very High-Resolution Satellite Stereo-Pairs". *Remote Sensing* 14 (4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14040849>.
- Ullah, Amin, Syed Myhammad Anwar, Jianqiang Li, Lubna Nadeem, Tariq Mahmood, Amjad Rehman, e Tanzila Saba. 2024. "Smart cities: the role of Internet of Things and machine learning in realizing a data-

centric smart environment”. *Complex & Intelligent Systems* 10 (1): 1607–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40747-023-01175-4>.

USDA Natural Resources Conservation. 2024. “USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service”. USDA Natural Resources Conservation Website. 3 de setembro de 2024. <https://www.nrcs.usda.gov>.

Vivone, Gemine. 2019. “Chapter 2.3 - Pansharpening”. Em *Hyperspectral Imaging*, editado por José Manuel Amigo, 32:69–91. *Data Handling in Science and Technology*. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63977-6.00005-5>.

Xu, Haowen, Femi Omitaomu, Soheil Sabri, Sisi Zlatanova, Xiao Li, e Yongze Song. 2024. “Leveraging Generative AI for Urban Digital Twins: A Scoping Review on the Autonomous Generation of Urban Data, Scenarios, Designs, and 3D City Models for Smart City Advancement”. *arXiv e-prints*, maio, arXiv:2405.19464. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.19464>.

Yuan, Qiangqiang, Huanfeng Shen, Tongwen Li, Zhiwei Li, Shuwen Li, Yun Jiang, Hongzhang Xu, et al. 2020. “Deep learning in environmental remote sensing: Achievements and challenges”. *Remote Sensing of Environment* 241:111716. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.111716>.

Zhang, Xingxing, Jingchun Shen, Puneet Kumar Saini, Marco Lovati, Mengjie Han, Pei Huang, e Zhihua Huang. 2021. “Digital Twin for Accelerating Sustainability in Positive Energy District: A Review of Simulation Tools and Applications”. *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities* 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsc.2021.663269>.

Zhu, Xiao Xiang, Devis Tuia, Lichao Mou, Gui-Song Xia, Liangpei Zhang, Feng Xu, e Friedrich Fraundorfer. 2017. “Deep Learning in Remote Sensing: A Comprehensive Review and List of Resources”. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine* 5 (4): 8–36. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MGRS.2017.2762307>.